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on Sustainable organic amendment applications from a soil
and ground water management perspective
-learning, training, and knowledge exchange activity-

02-06. June 2025, Novi Sad, Serbia

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REMOVAL OF MANGANESE IONS FROM WATER USING MAGNETITE NANOPARTICLES

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Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) represent a category of nanomaterials whose behavior can be controlled through magnetic fields, showcasing substantial potential across diverse environmental applications. Among these, magnetite nanoparticles (Fe_3O_4) are particularly prevalent due to their low toxicity and favorable biocompatibility. Typically, pristine MNPs are synthesized from iron salts via the co-precipitation method in an alkaline medium. Magnetite particles were known as good adsorbents which demonstrated high effectiveness for eliminating metal ions from water. This study explores the utilization of commercial magnetite nanoparticles (CAS: 1317-61-9) as an adsorbent for the removal of manganese ion (Mn^{2+}) from groundwater with relatively high Mn^{2+} content (600 $\mu\text{g/L}$). Research was conducted on groundwater from the territory of the city of Laktaši, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina, which is used for water supply to the population. Using the magnetite nanoparticles in a concentration of 5 g/L, a manganese ion removal efficiency of 98% is achieved after 1 hour of water treatment. The Mn^{2+} content remaining in the groundwater after treatment is 13.0 $\mu\text{g/L}$, achieving the values for manganese ion content in drinking water prescribed by the regulations of the Republic of Serbia (< 50 $\mu\text{g/L}$) (Official Gazette SRJ, No. 42/98 and 44/99; Official Gazette RS, No. 28/2019). The high efficiency of using magnetite particles for the removal of manganese ions highlights the potential of this material for use as an adsorbent in water purification.

Keywords: High cost-efficiency material, Groundwater treatment, Adsorption tests

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